

Demography and prevalence of irritable bowel syndrome in Northern Central India

Mohmmmd Abdullha*¹, Vandana Rajak², Najmul Sehar³, Khem Chand⁴, Yasmin Fatima⁵,
Mohammad Asif Qurashi, Abdul Mateen⁶

1-Research Officer Incharge, 2-Research Officer (U) Clinical Research Unit Bhopal CCRUM, 3-Deputy Director CRIUM. Lucknow, 4-Research officer (U), CRIUM. Lucknow, 5- Research Officer Incharge CRU Burhanpur. CCRUM, 6-Reserch Associate (U), Clinical Research Unit Bhopal Under CCRUM Ministry of Ayush Govt. of India.

*Corresponding Author: Mohmmmd Abdullha Research Officer Incharge Clinical Research Unit Bhopal under CCRUM Ministry of Ayush Govt. of India.

Received: Nov 24, 2025

Accepted: Dec 26, 2025

Published: Dec 30, 2025

Abstract- irritable bowel syndrome is common functional digestive disorders which reduce the quality of life and usually affect the productive age so it's also cause great economical loss. This study was an observational study designed by clinical research unit Bhopal and other institutes like CRIUM Lukhnow & CRU Burhanpur actively support and participate in this study. Following study suggest house wife most commonly affected according professional status, young age 30-40 Yrs is more prone. Adolescent of 10-15 & 15-20 Yrs age also suffering & No and ratio of this age group move to higher side due to increase stress in this age.

IBS clinically characterised by abdominal pain or abdominal discomfort with altered bowel function and feeling of incomplete evacuation of bowels, consistency of stool usually altered and associated with mucous disturbance of gut flora and gut brain axis, previous infection & visceral sensitivity and inflammatory conditions also plays important role in physio pathology of IBS. Over all study suggest the no age is safe and disease reduce the quality of life and affect the productivity of nation.

Key-Word- IBS, Maghas, Functional, Digestive Disorders,

Introduction- irritable bowel syndrome is a chronic digestive disorder and characterised by griping and abdominal pain with alteration in intestinal movements and ultimately result into diarrhoea and constipation in alternate fashion and sometimes both features present. In some time, ^{[1][2][3][4]} these all clinical features present without any anatomical changes and without any biochemical changes^{[7][9]}

Some patient of irritable bowel syndrome also reported non painful abdominal discomfort associated with anxiety, depression and visceral/somatic pain related symptoms^{[3][4][7][9]} irritable bowel syndrome considered as functional intestinal disorders or disorder of intestinal motility and more recently its considered as gut disorder^{[3][4][5][6]}. Irritable bowel syndrome is a common gastrointestinal disorder with worldwide prevalence ^[5]. According the perversely collected data in India the prevalence of IBS is 4.2% both sex affected by IBS but female ratio is slightly higher than male ratio^[5].Prevalence of IBS is higher in low socio economic population than high economic status population^[6], school going adolescents and adult usually equally suffer from IBS^[6]. Usually IBS start in adolescent age, IBS is not a life threatening condition but it reduce the quality of life^{[7][8][9][15][16]}. IBS shows a significant impact on patient quality of life due to physical suffering, psychological comorbidities, social disabilities and economic non productivity.^{[9][16][17]} Patho physiology of IBS is poorly under stool and treatment of IBS usually based on reduction of symptoms and improve the quality of life^{[9][10][11][12][15]}. Northern India and central India demographical and geography slight diversities but having the multiple similarities Ie. A large population live in village and belong to the low socioeconomic condition ^[9] similar diet and culture, and fast urbanization leads to rapid changes in life style.

Clinical features & diagnosis of IBS-

Rome Criteria is most widely accepted for establishment a diagnosis of IBS and severity of abdominal pain is the base of Rome Criteria, but in India Rome Criteria are less sensitive to establish the diagnosis of IBS. But various studies suggest that only 70% patient complaints the pain abdomen and 30% patient present of lower GI symptoms and abdominal bloating is another associated features. In India the establishment of diagnosis in case of IBS it considered as abdominal discomfort with pain ^[9] or abdominal bloating.

In Indian scenario the diagnosis of IBS established as follows.

- 1- Abdominal pain and cramping related to the bowel ie. Diarrhoea, constipation or both.
- 2- Bloating of gases and fullness of abdomen
- 3- Change in stool consistency ie. Stool becomes watery or constipation depending on types of IBS.
- 4- Mucous in stool
- 5- Urgency to have a bowel movement.
- 6- Sensation of incomplete evacuation of after a bowel movement ^{[7][10]}

Types- irritable bowel syndrome into three types.

IBS-C- when IBS associated with constipation or constipation is the main features.

IBS-D- when IBS associated with diarrhoea or loose or watery stool is the main feature.

IBS-U- when IBS is not classified in above mention types or when IBS associated with multiple features its usually found in children's & adolescent ^{[1][2][4][7][12][13]}.

Causes- various factors affect the intestinal motility, digestion and produce the IBS.

- 1- Abnormal gut motility or irregular muscles contraction of intestine.
- 2- Gut micro biota or imbalance or disturbed gut flora.
- 3- Visceral hypersensitivity Ie. Increased sensitivity of intestine to pain.
- 4- Gut brain axis disturbances- Ie. Due to communication issue between gut and brain.
- 5- Diet – certain foods may produce the IBS due to its intolerance to intestine i.e., Coeliac disease^{[1][2][3][10][11][12][13][14]}

Unani aspect of irritable bowel syndrome (Maghas)-

Ancient Unani scholar described the irritable bowel syndrome under the head of Maghas and they describe the Maghas as it's a painful condition of intestine ^{[18][19][21][22][23]}.

Jeelani Ghulam describe the Maghas in there text, Maghas is a painful spasm of small intestine and he also the Qarshi describe Maghas is the painful and spasmodic condition of intestine. Either it in reference in small intestine or large intestine and further mentioned the difference with Qolanj (large intestinal obstruction) as absolute constipation is compulsory in Qolanj. And in Maghas (IBS) recurrent bowel movement with evacuation of stool and persistent desire to evacuate the intestine ^{[20][21]}.

Types – Unani scholar describe various types of Maghas in the classical literature of Unani, they describes the following types on the base of causative factors.

- 1- Maghas-e-Reehi(IBS due to flatulence)
- 2- Maghas-e-Balghami
- 3- Maghas-e-Safravi
- 4- Maghas-e-Saudawi
- 5- Maghas-e-Iltehabi
- 6- Maghas-e-Sufli
- 7- Maghas-e-Atfal

Methodology –

Present study was an observational study and data collected through patient whose attend the OPD of selected centres or mobile programme OPD. Study design by clinical research unit Bhopal worked under central council for research in Unani medicine. Which is the apex body for research in Unani medicine and autonomous organization of Ministry of Ayush Government of India. Clinical research unit Burhanpur and central research institute of Unani medicine Lucknow both worked under central council for research in Unani medicine, Ministry of Ayush Government of India. Actively participated in this programme, various district units of UP state health Deptt. also supported and actively participated and help in the collection of data, to achieve the goal we collect the data from 1 April 2024 – 31 March 2025 total 11345 patient short listed who suffering from gastro intestinal ailments (Digestive disorders out of 45417 patient and 2975 patient was suffering from IBS)

Observation & demographic data

1- Distribution of GIT disorder according to %

S N	Total no of patient	No of patient GIT disorder	% of age
1	45417	11345	25%

2- Distribution of IBS in GIT disorders

S N	Total no of patient of GIT disorders	Total no of patient IBS	% of age
1	11345	2975	26.223%

3- Distribution of IBS according

S N	Name of Mijaz	No of patient	% of age
1	Balghami (Phlegmate)	913	30.689%
2	Safravi(Bilious)	615	20.672%
3	Damwi(Sanguine)	734	24.672%
4	Saudawi(Malencholic)	713	23.966%
	Total	2975	100%

4- Distribution of IBS according to profession

S N	Name to profession	No of patient	% of age
1	Student	315	10.588%
2	Shopkeeper	432	14.521%
3	Mechanic	211	7.092%
4	Serviceman	395	13.277%
5	Labourer	317	10.655%
6	Driver	337	11.327%
7	Teacher	105	5.529%
8	House wife	437	14.689%
9	Engineers	120	4.033%
10	Formers	306	10.285%
	Total	2975	99.996%

5-Distribution of IBS according to economic status

S N	Name to economic status	No of patient	% of age
1	Lower economic status	1638	55.058%
2	Lower middle economic status	408	13.714%
3	Middle economic status	791	26.588%
4	High economic status	138	4.638%
	Total	2975	99.998%

6- Distribution of IBS according to age group

S N	Name to age group	No of patient	% of age
1	11-15 Yrs	103	3.462%
2	16-20 Yrs	169	5.680%
3	21-30 Yrs	631	21.210%
4	31-40 Yrs	1489	50.050%
5	41-50 Yrs	384	12.907%
6	51-60 Yrs	199	6.689%
	Total	2975	99.998%

7- Distribution of IBS according to religion

S N	Name to religion	No of patient	% of age
1	Hindu	1233	41.445%
2	Muslim	1501	50.453%
3	Other	241	8.100%
	Total	2975	99.998%

8- Distribution of IBS according to alcoholic/non alcoholic nature

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Alcoholic	1755	58.991%
2	Non alcoholic	1220	41.008%
	Total	2975	99.999%

9- Distribution of IBS according to Tobacco consumer/Non tobacco consumer

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Tobacco consumer	1699	57.109%
2	Non tobacco consumer	1276	42.890%
	Total	2975	99.999%

10- Distribution of IBS according to sleeping habits

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Good sleep(8 hour& more)	535	17.983%
2	Average sleep(6-8 hour)	813	27.327%
3	Disturbed sleep(less than 6 hour)	1627	54.689%
	Total	2975	99.999%

Prevalence of IBS with upper abdominal symptoms with dyspepsia

IBS and functional dyspepsia (FD) having common Pathophysiological mechanism like. Visceral hypersensitivity & closely related to each other.

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	IBS with F.D. feature over lap	933	31.361%
2	IBS without F.D. feature	2042	68.638%
	Total	2975	99.999%

Prevalence of IBS with associated pain

Some patient not feature the pain & some patient having the pain specifically recurrent pain

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	IBS with pain	1911	64.235%
2	IBS without pain	1064	35.764%
	Total	2975	99.999%

Prevalence of IBS according to sub typing of IBS

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	IBS with diarrhoea	1433	48.168%
2	IBS with constipation	745	25.042%
3	IBS with mixed feature or IBS-M	699	23.495%
4	IBS with uncategorised IBS-U	98	3.294%
	Total	2975	99.999%

Prevalence of IBS with abdominal feature

Prevalence of IBS lower abdominal features data collected and analysed on following point

A- Prevalence of IBS with incomplete evacuation of bowel

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Incomplete evacuation of bowel	1941	65.243%
2	Patient with clear evacuation of bowel	1034	34.756%
	Total	2975	99.999%

B- Prevalence of IBS with change in frequency of stool

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Increased frequency of stool	1111	37.344%
2	Decreased frequency of stool	925	31.092%
3	No change in frequency of stool	939	31.563%
	Total	2975	99.999%

C- Prevalence of IBS with urgency in passing the stool

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Increased urgency	1229	41.310%
2	Normal passing stool	1746	58.689%
	Total	2975	99.999%

D- Prevalence of IBS with straining to stool

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	IBS with straining of stool	1571	52.806%
2	IBS without straining of stool	1404	47.193%
	Total	2975	99.999%

E- Prevalence of IBS with mucous in stool

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	IBS with mucous in stool	1735	58.319%
2	IBS without mucous in stool	1240	41.680%
	Total	2975	99.999%

F- Prevalence of IBS when pain relive after a bowel movement

S N	Name to category	No of patient	% of age
1	Pain relived after a bowel	1769	59.462%
2	Pain not relived after bowel	1206	40.537%
	Total	2975	99.999%

Discussion- irritable bowel syndrome is common functional digestive disorder and all type population affected by this syndrome, demographic analysis are as follows.

Present study suggest the Phlegmatic nature people most common affected with 30.689% and according the profession house wife commonly affected with 14.689% and shopkeepers with very close 14.521% 2nd position according economic status, lower economic status patient most affected with 55.058% in the age group. No age is safe but 31-40 Yrs age most affected with 50.050% age according the religion Muslim religion person in top with 50.453%, according the habit alcoholic consuming of person 58.991% with top position and 57.109% top in tobacco chewer person. According sleeping habits disturbed sleep person (sleep less than 6 hour) are top with 54.689%.

Conclusion- Present data suggest irritable bowel syndrome are a common functional digestive disease/syndrome and collected data after analysis suggest IBS having the strong relation with low economic status with mental worker, sedentary life, its also associated with stressful condition. Which severely reduce the quality of life and ultimately affected the productivity of nation. One another thing also seen in this study the children of school going age also suffering this syndrome. Which is due to increase load of education and increase the stress in this age which is an alarming feature to health authorities specially health planners and education planners also.

Acknowledgment- Author express the sincere thanks to Dr N Zaheer Ahmad Director General of Central Council for Research in Unani Medicine for his kind co-operation and Dr Younis Iftikhar Munshi Deputy Director General of Central Council for Research in Unani Medicine due to always support me.

Author also express the sincere thanks to health Deptt. of UP Govt specially CMO's of those districts who co-operate me and unbound support and provide the data of patient.

Conflict of interest- Author declare the no conflict of interest i.e. in research authorship and publication of this article.

References-

- 1- Jenifer k. Lehrar et. al, irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) practice & essentials background Pathophysiology update 15 may 2024.
- 2- Over review- irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) john Hopkins Medicine.org /health.
- 3- Siobhain M.O' Mahony- irritable bowel syndrome and stress related psychiatric Co. morbidities PMID 28233180, DOI 10.1007/164, 2016.
- 4- Emiran- A. Mayer et al, the Neurobiology of irritable bowel syndrome Mol. Psychiatric 2023 April 28(4), 1451-1465 DOI.
- 5- Huma, Younis Iftekhar Munshi et al, Demographical and clinical features of patient with IBS: an epidemiological study in Kashmir.
- 6- Rehman S. et al, assessment of IBS symptoms among patients of lower socio economic condition starta attending medicine OPD in a tertiary care hospital in South Delhi, international journal advance in medicine 2017 August 4(4) DOI ;<http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2349-3933>, ijam 2017,3243.
- 7- Pan G et al, epidemiological study of IBS in beijing; stratified randomized study by the cluster sampling, chin med.j.(Engl) 2000,113;35;39.
- 8- Mayer E.A.IBS,N.Engl.J.Medicine 2008;358;1692-99.
- 9- M. M. Rehman et. al, Deptt. of Gastroenterology Dhaka medical college epidemiological and clinical perspective of IBS in India, Bangladesh & Malaysia world journal of Gastroenterology, October 7, 2017;23(37);6788-6801.
- 10- Govind k Makharia et. al, prevalence of IBS, A community based study from northern India. Journal of Neuro Gastrointestinal motility volume17, No 1 January 2017.
- 11- Chandan Sharma et. al, prevalence of irritable bowel syndrome in rural belt of Jammu- international journal of research & review volume 8, issue 1.Januray 2021.
- 12- Eyad, A Makkawy et. al, prevalence and risk factor and management of IBS in Saudi Arabia; A systemic review. DOI; 10.7759 cureus. 47440.
- 13- Ashwani porwal et. al, the IBS under standry its type and treatment options. World journal of advance research and reviews 2024,22(01),720-728.
- 14- Yu, Tung Lai et. al, epidemiology of clinical features and presenting pattern of IBS in Taiwan. Pharmacol 16 December 2021 section Gastrointestinal and Hepatic pharmacology volume 12.2021.

- 15- Chua A. S. Prevention of IBS in northern India Neurogastrology motil 2011;17;6-8.
- 16- Long starch GF et. al, functional bowel disorders, Gastroenterology 2006;130;1480-91.
- 17- Rajendra S, Alqhuiddin S- Prevalence of IBS in multi ethnic Asian population aliment pharmacol 2004;19;704-06.
- 18- Samar Qandi, Moilijat Shrah Asbab, Volume 2, page no 602, Urdu translation by Hakim Kabiruddin Publishing Yrs NA. Published by Hikmat book depot Hyderabad.
- 19- Baghdadi Ibn-e-Hubal, Kitab Al Mukhtarat fit tib, volume 3 page 243, Urdu translation by CCRUM, Deptt.t of Ayush MOH New Delhi publishing yrs 2004.
- 20- Jeelani Ghulam, Makhjan ul Ilaj volume 1&2 reprint 2014. Page No 551 published by Idara kitab ul shifa darya ganj New Delhi.
- 21- Arjani Akbar, Tib-e-Akbar Page No 495, Publishing yrs 2016, Published by faisal international Pataudi house.
- 22- Khan Azam Ikseer-e-Azam, Urdu translation by Hakim Kabiruddin publishing yrs 2011, Page No 624-628. Published by Idara kitab ul shifa darya ganj New Delhi.
- 23- Khan Mohd shamim, Rehbare Moalijat Page No 113. 3rd edition 2011, Published by Idara kitab ul shifa darya ganj New Delhi.
- 24- Avicenna;Al Qanoon Fit tib, Page No 955-56, Urdu translation by Hakim Ghulam Husain Kantoori. Publishing year 2014, published by Idara kitab ul shifa darya ganj New Delhi.